

Analysis of the Relationship between Factorials and Integers

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Abstract: This paper presents theorems in factorials and also discusses the relationship between factorial function or factorials and integers. The results of factorial theorems can be used as applications in computing and cybersecurity to develop algorithms and computer programs.

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1. Introduction

Integers play a vital role in factorial functions or factorials [1-10]. We know that factorials and binomial coefficients including combinations and permutations refer to integers. Theorems in factorials have several applications in computing, science, and engineering.

Definition: Factorial of any non-negative integer p , denoted by $p!$, is defined as a product of all nonnegative integers less than or equal to p .

2. A Theorem in Factorials

The theorem states that the factorials of integer p and q ($0 \leq p \leq q$) such that $p!$ divided by $p!$ is an integer, Also, $(p + q)!$ divided by $p!$, $q!$, or $p!q!$ is an integer.

Thorem 2.1: For integers $0 \leq p \leq q$,

$$\frac{q!}{p!}; \frac{(p + q)!}{p!}; \frac{(p + q)!}{q!}; \text{ and } \frac{(p + q)!}{p!q!} \text{ are integers.}$$

Proof. $0! = 1$; $1! = 1$; $2! = 1 \times 2 = 2$; $3! = 1 \times 2 \times 3 = 6$; \dots ; $p!$ for $p \geq 0$ are integers.

If $q = p \geq 0$, then $q! = p! \geq 1$. If $q > p$, $q! = p! \times (p + 1)(p + 2)(p + 3) \dots (q - 2)(q - 1)q$.

$\frac{q!}{p!} = (p + 1)(p + 2)(p + 3) \dots (q - 2)(q - 1)q$ is an integer. As $\frac{q!}{p!}$ is an integer,

$\frac{(p + q)!}{p!}$ and $\frac{(p + q)!}{q!}$ are integers. Let us prove that $\frac{(p + q)!}{p!q!}$ is an integer.

$$\frac{(p + q)!}{p!q!} = \frac{(p + 1)(p + 2)(p + 3) \dots (p + q)}{q!}. \text{ Let } p = 0. \text{ Then, } \frac{(p + 1)(p + 2) \dots (p + q)}{q!} = 1$$

and let $p = 1$. $\frac{2 \times 3 \times 4 \times \dots \times q(q + 1)}{q!} = \frac{q! \times (q + 1)}{q!} = q + 1$ is an integer, that is,

If $p \geq 1$, then $\frac{(p + 1)(p + 2)(p + 3) \dots (p + q)}{q!} \geq (q + 1)$ are integers for $p = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Hence, theorem is proved.

Note that $p! \leq q! \leq p!q! \leq (p+q)! \Rightarrow \frac{(p+q)!}{p!q!} \leq \frac{(p+q)!}{q!} \leq \frac{(p+q)!}{p!}$.

We can also prove the theorem by binomial coefficient.

The binomial coefficient is $\binom{q}{p} = \frac{q!}{p!(q-p)!}$. If $q = p$, then $\binom{p}{p} = \frac{p!}{p!(p-p)!} = 1$.

If $q > p$, $\binom{q}{p} = \frac{q!}{p!(q-p)!} > 1$ is an integer. For example, $\binom{3}{2} = \frac{3!}{2!1!} = 3$.

Binomial coefficient $\binom{p+q}{p} = \frac{(p+q)!}{p!q!} = l$ is an integer, ($l \geq 0$).

Note that $\frac{(p+q)!}{p!q!} = l \Rightarrow (p+q)! = l \times p! \times q!$.

Theorem 2.2 : For any k nonnegative integers n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots and n_k ,

$$(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)! = (a_1 \times a_2 \times a_3 \times \dots \times a_{k-1}) \times n_1! \times n_2! \times n_3! \times \dots \times n_k!,$$

$$\text{that is, } \left(\sum_{i=1}^k n_i \right)! = A \prod_{i=1}^k n_i!,$$

where $A = a_1 \times a_2 \times a_3 \times \dots \times a_{k-1}$ and $A, a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_{k-1}$ are nonnegative integers.

Proof. Let $x = n_2 + n_3 + n_4 + \dots + n_k$. Then, $(n_1 + x) = a_1 \times n_1! \times x!$ (refer to theorem 2.1), that is, $(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)! = a_1 \times n_1! \times (n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)!$.

Similarly, if we apply the same way to prove each of the sums, we get as follows:

$$(n_2 + n_3 + n_4 + \dots + n_k)! = a_2 \times n_2! \times (n_3 + n_4 + \dots + n_k)!; (n_3 + n_4 + n_5 + \dots + n_k)! = a_3 \times n_3! \times (n_4 + n_5 + \dots + n_k)!; (n_4 + n_5 + n_6 + \dots + n_k) = a_4 \times n_4! \times (n_5 + n_6 + \dots + n_k)!; \dots, \text{ and } (n_{k-1} + n_k) = a_{k-1} \times n_{k-1}! \times n_k.$$

If we substitute these results step by step in $a_1 \times n_1! \times (n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)!$, that is, $a_1 \times n_1! \times (n_2 + n_3 + n_4 \dots + n_k)! = a_1 \times n_1! \times (a_2 \times n_2! \times (n_3 + n_4 \dots + n_k)!)$ $= a_1 \times a_2 \times n_1! \times n_2! \times (a_3 \times n_3! \times (n_4 + \dots + n_k)!)$, etc., we obtain the following result.

$$(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)! = (a_1 \times a_2 \times a_3 \times \dots \times a_{k-1}) \times n_1! \times n_2! \times n_3! \times \dots \times n_k!,$$

$$\text{that is, } \left(\sum_{i=1}^k n_i \right)! = A \prod_{i=1}^k n_i!, \quad \text{where } A = a_1 \times a_2 \times a_3 \times \dots \times a_{k-1}.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

For instance,

If $n_1 = n_2 = n_3 = \dots = n_k = n$. Then, $(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)! = (k \times n)!$.

If $n_1 = n_2 = n_3 = \dots = n_k = 0$. Then, $(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)! = (k \times 0)! = 0! = 1$.

If $n_1 = n_2 = n_3 = \dots = n_k = 1$. Then, $(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)! = (k \times 1)! = k!$.

If $n_1 = n_2 = n_3 = \dots = n_k = 2$. Then, $(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)! = (k \times 2)! = (2k)!$.

If $n_1 = n_2 = n_3 = \dots = n_k = k$. Then, $(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)! = (k \times k)! = k^2!$.

This idea can help to the researchers working in computational science, management, science, and engineering.

3. Conclusion

In this article, an innovative combinatorial technique and theorem are introduced and the theorem states that the factorial of sum of any k nonnegative integers is equal to multiple of the product of factorials of the k nonnegative integers. This methodological advance can enable the researchers working in computational science, management, science and engineering to solve the most real life problems and meet today's challenges [11].

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